

USING SENTENCE COMBINING STRATEGY AND WRITING PERFORMANCE IN ENGLISH OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The present study is conceptualized to determine the usefulness and effectiveness of sentence combining strategy as method for helping students produce and construct more syntactically mature sentences. This is initiated to help the students improve their writing performance in English and make sentence construction in writing more automatic and less labored. After conducting the pretest and posttest, evaluation was made on the gathered data using T-test. This was used to determine if there is a significant difference between the means of two groups, which may be related in certain features. Moreover, a t-test is used as a hypothesis testing tool, which allows testing of an assumption applicable to a population. There are four stages and levels of writers such as 11.25 – 15.00 Advanced, 7.50 – 11.24 Proficient, 3.75 – 7.49 Developing, and 0.00 – 3.74 Beginning. The findings revealed that majority of the respondents are female with the frequency of 20 or 66.6% of the total respondents, while 10 or 33.3% are male. 50% of the respondents are proficient in their performance in writing in terms of grammar. 26.6% are developing and 13.4% are advanced. Based on the pretest result, no students are classified to be beginning in their grammar skills relative to their writing performance. In terms of the mean score performance in grammar, 8.53 with 2.46 standard deviation is classified as proficient. This infers that the students are grammatically proficient, can identify simple grammatical errors, and can express themselves with simple grammatical accuracy. The standing of experimental students before and after instruction is 86.7% of the respondents garnered a score classified as advanced level. 13.3% are in the proficient level and 0% for both developing and beginning level. This means that there was statistically significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents in their writing performance before and after using sentence combining strategy in terms of grammar. The mean performance score of the respondents is 13.67 with the standard deviation of 1.35. The mean revealed that the students have an advanced or exceptional performance in their grammar-related writing performance. In terms of grammar a computed t-value of 11.631 and a p-value of 0.000 shows a significant difference on the pretest and posttest performance of the respondents. Therefore, it could be assumed that Sentence Combining Strategy is a great tool to improve the writing performance of the selected grade 9 students in Sta. Catalina Integrated National High School. Its positive impact on the writing performance of the respondents affirmed that there is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest scores of the respondents in their writing performance before and after using sentence combining strategy. Thus, the null hypothesis is “accepted”. The following recommendations were drawn based from the results of the study. Sentence combining strategy will be endorsed to English teachers as their reference to help their students improve their writing performance

in English. English teachers should teach their students to use a variety of sentences in their writing. As an educator, strengthen the foundation of grammar lessons to enhance the writing performance of the students in English. Students are encouraged to practice sentence combining strategy in writing composition. Future researchers may use this as their reference when doing another research work about Sentence Combining Strategy and Writing Performance of grade 9 in English. Further relevant studies may be conducted to make an improvement on the weaknesses of this research to conduct a better study.

Keywords: grammar skills, writing performance, grammatical accuracy, Sentence Combining Strategy